

IMPACT OF FOREIGN AID AND INFRASTRUCTURAL DEVELOPMENT IN NIGERIA: A STUDY OF NIGERIAN RAILWAY CORPORATION

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Abstract

Infrastructural aid, regardless of its magnitude, forms the cornerstone of the international aid system. It plays a crucial role in poverty alleviation, creation of job opportunities, and addressing infrastructural deficits. In doing this, the aid recipient has to be prudent in its management of the aid received. For aid to be effective, the recipient country must manage it prudently. Mismanagement can lead to dependency and impede local investment and infrastructure development. Given the topic's broad scope, this research focuses on the impact of foreign aid on Nigeria's infrastructural development, specifically through the lens of the Nigerian Railway Corporation. This study examines the relationship between foreign aid inflow and the Nigerian Railway Corporation. It explores the relationship between foreign aid inflows and the effectiveness of infrastructure improvements, using dependency theory as a theoretical framework. Drawing on secondary data sources, the research assesses Nigeria's economic trajectory and potential advancements that could have been achieved with optimal utilisation of prior allocations. The findings highlight the diverse implications of foreign aid on infrastructure projects, emphasising both the challenges and opportunities for sustainable economic growth.

Keywords: Foreign Aid, Rail Way System, Infrastructure, Infrastructural Development

Background of the Study

In the realm of international relations, foreign aid—also known as international assistance, overseas assistance, or external support—represents the voluntary transfer of resources from one nation to another. Governments utilise aid for diverse purposes, such as signalling diplomatic intentions, strengthening military alliances, rewarding favourable behaviour, expanding cultural influence, facilitating

infrastructure for resource extraction, or creating pathways for commercial access. Humanitarian concerns and diplomatic motives frequently drive aid initiatives, which can originate from individuals, private organisations, or governmental entities. Definitions of aid vary widely across countries; for instance, the United States ceased including military aid in its foreign aid reporting in 1958. Overseas Development Assistance (ODA) remains the predominant metric for assessing aid contributions.

Aid is classified based on several criteria, including its intended use, attached conditions, funding source, and urgency. Various types of aid align closely with their specified objectives: military aid enhances the defence capabilities of allied nations, while humanitarian aid responds to crises such as natural disasters. The terms of aid—whether it takes the form of grants, gifts, concessional loans, or a hybrid—reflect the motivations of the donor country. Aid sources range from governmental assistance to faith-based assistance provided by religious institutions. Delivery methods vary as well: bilateral aid involves direct government-to-government transfers, whereas multilateral aid, administered by organisations like the World Bank, distributes assistance from multiple donors to numerous recipients. Private donations from individuals or corporations are typically managed by charities or philanthropic organisations, which aggregate and channel contributions to beneficiary countries.

This study employs a foundational economic model integrating foreign investment and public infrastructure in the context of economic analysis to investigate how increased labour impacts the production of private goods, public infrastructure, foreign investment, welfare, and peculiarization. It proposes strategies to expedite economic development, emphasising that sustained economic growth alone may not suffice.

In 2012, despite previous robust growth, the Nigerian economy experienced a slowdown. Unemployment increased from 21 percent in 2010 to 24 percent in 2011, with persistently high poverty rates only marginally decreasing from 48 percent in 2004 to 46 percent in 2010. However, 2012 witnessed enhanced exports and reduced imports, resulting in a 59 percent improvement in the trade balance and a 24 percent rise in foreign direct investment (FDI) compared to 2011. Official Development Assistance (ODA) decreased from USD 2.0 billion in 2010 to USD 1.8 billion in 2011, while total FDI reached USD 8.9 billion, constituting 20 percent of Africa's total FDI (World Bank, 2013).

This study aims to evaluate infrastructure development's impact on economic growth from a Nigerian perspective. Insufficient infrastructure investment poses a significant hurdle to Nigeria's aspirations of achieving top-20 global economy status

by 2020. Despite years of economic expansion, the lack of infrastructure, coupled with high poverty rates and unemployment, has hindered the transformation of growth into sustainable development.

Statement of the Problem

When managed effectively, foreign aid and infrastructure development aim to enhance a country's infrastructure for the collective benefit of its people, fostering employment, reducing unemployment, and improving citizens' well-being. However, mismanagement and misallocation of aid lead to infrastructural deficits, hindering business growth. Insufficient electricity generation raises the cost of goods, while inadequate transportation infrastructure, such as poor roads and a lack of a reliable rail system, complicates the distribution of bulk agricultural produce. These challenges could be mitigated through judicious use of foreign aid. One of the primary goals of aid is to develop infrastructure, creating employment opportunities that uplift the masses and alleviate poverty. In Nigeria, however, aid intended for infrastructural development has often been diverted for personal gain, mismanaged, and awarded to unqualified contractors. Many governmental policies prioritise partisan interests over development, resulting in deficits in infrastructure, including roads, power, rail, and technological advancement.

Due to constraints in time and resources, this study focuses specifically on the relationship between foreign aid and infrastructural development within the Nigerian Railway Corporation. The research aims to assess how foreign aid impacts infrastructural development in Nigeria, concentrating on this specific area. The role of foreign aid and infrastructural development in the growth trajectory of developing nations has sparked considerable debate, particularly regarding its potential to alleviate poverty. In Nigeria and many other African and developing countries, there are various perspectives on the effectiveness of foreign aid and infrastructural development. These perspectives include beliefs that aid yields diminishing returns, that its effectiveness is influenced by external and climatic factors, that political conditions play a crucial role, and that institutional quality is a determining factor. Notably, there has been a significant increase in foreign aid directed towards infrastructural development in Nigeria in recent years. However, despite this increase, there remains a deficit in infrastructural development, particularly in rail transportation, even as other forms of investment, such as foreign direct investment, show signs of decline.

Research Question

Based on the above-stated problem, the study seeks to raise the following research questions:

1. Does foreign aid contribute to Nigeria's infrastructure development?
2. Is Nigeria's infrastructural development dependent on foreign aid?

3. Are there deficits in infrastructural development in Nigeria with reference to the Nigerian Railway Corporation?

Review of General Literature

Nigeria, like many Sub-Saharan African nations, faces significant infrastructural deficits that impede its economic progress. Recognising the critical role of infrastructure in drawing foreign investment, the Nigerian government aims to address these challenges to meet its goal of becoming one of the top 20 economies by 2020. However, achieving this goal necessitates substantial investment, projected at over \$100 billion of its GDP within the next five years. Much of Nigeria's current infrastructure, constructed during the 1970s oil boom, has suffered from neglect and underinvestment, leading to its deterioration.

Government involvement in infrastructure development is driven by factors such as high capital costs, construction risks, and lengthy financial payback periods. Nevertheless, economic reforms and fluctuations in the oil market have led to neglect and underinvestment in infrastructure, affecting sectors like transportation, education, health, and housing. This neglect has resulted in poor road networks, unreliable power supply, inadequate aviation and railway services, and numerous abandoned projects across the country.

Inadequate infrastructure in developing countries like Nigeria not only hampers domestic productivity and competitiveness but also deters foreign investment. Scholars such as Wheeler, Moody, Loree, Guisinger, Richard, Morisset, Asiedu, and Sekkat have highlighted the essential role of infrastructure in attracting foreign direct investment (FDI). They argue that well-developed infrastructure lowers costs for firms and improves the investment climate, leading to higher returns on investment (ROI). Infrastructure—including roads, railways, ports, communication networks, and electricity—alongside political stability, enhances productivity and makes a location more appealing to investors. Studies indicate that countries with better infrastructure tend to attract more investment, underscoring the importance of addressing infrastructure challenges for Nigeria's economic development and its ability to attract FDI.

Infrastructure development can give nations like Nigeria a competitive advantage, particularly in attracting foreign investment. Edun underscores the importance of increasing infrastructure investment and reducing construction material costs, such as cement, to establish a solid foundation for attracting FDI. Unlike traditional views, recent growth models recognise the enduring impact of FDI on economic growth. While older theories viewed FDI's influence as temporary due to diminishing returns, modern models emphasise its role in long-term growth through knowledge transfer. Barro and Sala-i-Martin contend that endogenous growth models enable

FDI to contribute to sustainable economic growth by facilitating knowledge transfer and other externalities, resulting in long-term growth benefits.

By integrating growth determinants, including FDI, into the model, the long-term impacts of FDI can be established, paving the way for technological spillover from developed to developing nations through FDI inflows. Supported by Bengoa and Sanchez-Robles (2003), De-Mello (1999), Obwona (2001), and Borensztein et al. (1998), the idea that FDI serves as a major channel for technology transfer, surpassing domestic investment in its contribution to growth, is confirmed. Using an endogenous growth model where technological advancement determines the long-term income growth rate, Bengoa and Sanchez-Robles (2003) argued that recipient countries must have adequate human capital, robust infrastructure, economic stability, and liberalised markets to attract sustained capital inflows conducive to long-term growth. Buckley et al. (2002) assert that the extent to which FDI drives growth depends on the economic and social conditions of the recipient country, suggesting that nations with high savings rates, open trade regimes, and advanced technology stand to gain more from increased FDI.

Railway systems are critical to driving economic development and growth because they serve as the backbone of production and distribution. They support agricultural development, industrial growth, and the establishment of residential, commercial, educational, and recreational areas along their corridors. Because of its capacity, safety, security, and cost-effectiveness for long-distance travel, rail transport is considered the core component of an integrated national transport system. Historically, rail transport has been a key driver of economic takeoff, expanding markets, and stimulating export sectors. Early rail lines played a significant role in fostering commerce, agricultural expansion, and settlement growth. Studies have shown a positive correlation between railway development and economic growth in various regions, including the American Midwest, Latin America, the US, Uruguay, and Colombia.

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Foreign Aid and Physical Capital Investment: The Nigerian Experience

Extensive research has explored the nexus between foreign aid and public investment. Studies by Lensink and Morrissey (1999), Hansen and Tarp (2000, 2001), and Mavrotas (2003) generally affirm that foreign aid boosts public investment in recipient nations. For instance, Levy (1987) analysed data from 39 least developed countries and found that a substantial share of aid to developing nations is directed towards investment. He observed that an increase in the aid-to-income ratio typically leads to a 0.86-point rise in the investment ratio. Hansen and Tarp (2000), summarising seven studies from 1972 to 1998, also report positive effects of aid on investment.

However, some studies highlight variations in this relationship among aid-receiving countries. Easterly (1999) examined 88 aid-recipient nations over three decades (1965-1995) and found a mixed impact of aid on public investment: negative in 36 countries, negative but insignificant in 17, positive in 23, and insignificant in 12. It should be noted that Easterly's analysis used a simple ordinary least squares (OLS) model, which might not account for certain biases. Conversely, Dollar and Easterly (1999) and Gomanee et al. (2005) found compelling evidence that aid has a significant positive effect on physical investment, contradicting Easterly's findings.

On average, a one percent increase in aid correlates with a 0.53 percent rise in the investment share of GDP, underscoring the considerable significance of aid. Recent theoretical work suggests maintaining modest expectations about the impact of foreign aid on physical investment. Rajan and Subramanian (2008), using a standard neoclassical production function framework, estimate that a 10% increase in aid inflows as a proportion of GDP might raise the growth rate by 1% to 2.5%, depending on the share of aid directed towards physical capital investment and its productivity effects.

In another study, Gyimah-Brempong and Racine (2010) employ panel data and the local linear kernel estimator (LLKE) to assess the impact of aid on physical capital investment in developing countries, particularly in less developed countries (LDCs). They evaluate the robustness of the aid-investment relationship using a variety of aid measures and policy environment indicators. Their findings show that external aid has a positive and significant effect on physical capital investment, consistent across different aid measures and policy contexts. Additionally, they observe that a more favourable policy environment is associated with higher investment rates, all other things being equal.

Factors Determining the Amount of Foreign Aid for Infrastructural Development

Stephan (2003) contended that public infrastructure plays a crucial role in supporting the private sector, while Paul et al. (2004) examined its effects on Canadian manufacturing industries. Fumagalli (2003) investigated the welfare implications of competition for foreign investment, and Hoffman (2003) empirically analysed the relationship between public infrastructure and capital inflows using comprehensive cross-sectional data. Their research collectively underscored a positive correlation between the availability of public infrastructure and capital inflows.

Numerous scholars emphasize the pivotal role of robust infrastructure in attracting foreign direct investment (FDI). Wheeler and Mody (1992), Loree and Guisinger (1995), Richard et al. (1999), Morrisset (2000), Asiedu (2002), and Sekkat et al. (2004) all concur that adequate infrastructure is essential for enabling foreign investors to operate efficiently. Insufficient public services or inadequate infrastructure can elevate operational costs for firms. Multinational corporations, driven by profit motives, seek to minimize costs by relocating to developing economies with lower labor expenses. However, they encounter challenges such as patent vulnerability and increased transportation costs due to communication barriers, which may deter investment in regions lacking adequate infrastructure.

Models explaining multinational and governmental investment decisions should integrate infrastructure, or its absence, as it significantly influences firms' cost structures. Enhanced infrastructure can improve the investment climate for FDI by reducing overall investment costs for foreign investors, thereby enhancing potential returns. Critical infrastructure components such as roads, ports, communication networks, and reliable electricity supply are anticipated to enhance productivity and attract higher levels of FDI. Wei (2000) proposed that locations with well-developed infrastructure are more appealing to investors than those without.

In Taiwan, an emerging economy with relatively advanced development, Bende-Nabende and Ford (1998) found that FDI contributes to growth by enhancing

infrastructure. Conversely, Elmawazinir, Saadi, and Ngouhouo (2005) demonstrated that FDI's impact on productivity growth in developing nations is generally less pronounced than in developed countries, citing technological deficiencies and varying levels of human capital as significant challenges for developing countries in harnessing FDI benefits.

Li and Liu (2005) examined the relationship between FDI and economic growth using panel data from 84 countries spanning from 1970 to 1999. They identified a significant endogenous relationship between FDI and economic growth from the mid-1980s onwards. FDI not only directly stimulates economic growth but also indirectly through interactions with factors like human capital and infrastructure development, underscoring the critical role of these factors in fostering technological advancement. However, they also noted a significant negative impact when FDI interacts with technological gaps, emphasising the importance of addressing these gaps for long-term growth.

Makki and Somwaru (2004) examined the role of FDI and trade in developing countries' economic growth over three decades (1971-2000) across 66 nations.

Developing Nigeria through Investments in Rail Transport

By 2003, Nigeria's railway network spanned approximately 3,557 kilometres of single-gauge track, much of which was inactive. The railway system was primarily composed of two main lines: one linking Lagos to Kano and another connecting Port Harcourt in Rivers State to Maiduguri in Borno State. These lines suffered from neglect until 2009, when substantial investments were initiated to revive Nigeria's dormant economic potential. Consequently, the country increasingly relied on road transport for moving bulk goods, leading to deteriorating road conditions and significant economic and human losses. The sole operational long-distance segment, running from Lagos to Kano, was refurbished in 2013 through efforts by the China Civil Engineering Construction Corporation (CCECC) and Costain West Africa.

Railway transportation is pivotal for land transport, playing an indispensable role in the socio-economic development of advanced economies. Hence, prioritising railways is crucial for Nigeria's ambition to rank among the world's top 20 economies by 2020. The construction of standard gauge tracks began with notable progress, including President Muhammadu Buhari's completion of the Abuja-Kaduna service in July 2016. Simultaneously, work on the Lagos-Ibadan section began with a target for completion by 2020.

Implementing the standard gauge rail system promises substantial economic benefits for Nigeria, including the transfer of skills and technology. Feasibility studies suggest the coastal rail project alone could create 50,000 direct job opportunities for

professionals and non-professionals, with an additional 100,000 indirect jobs during implementation. Moreover, operation, maintenance, and management of the coastal railway are expected to generate over 20,000 permanent jobs, including 26,000 professional roles and 23,800 non-professional positions.

Additional benefits include efficient transport of agricultural produce, alleviation of road congestion, savings in government expenditures, and prolonged road infrastructure lifespan. Railways also enhance land value along their routes, augmenting national wealth and providing affordable transport for all citizens. They facilitate labor and raw material movement, bolster industrial development, and ensure market stability during emergencies like floods and famines, including benefits extended to the Lagos-Kaduna standard gauge train services.

The Abuja-Kaduna standard gauge train service has positively impacted Nigeria's economy and the Nigerian Railway Corporation (NRC). Commuters now enjoy faster travel between Abuja and Kaduna, while the NRC benefits from enhanced skills, training, and technology from the CCECC. The NRC operates independently but occasionally consults Chinese technical staff, with 488 staff members compared to CCECC's 21. Local benefits include significant input from subcontractors and suppliers, generating about 2,400 direct local jobs annually during construction and totaling 17,000 over seven years.

Investing in the transportation sector, particularly the Nigerian Railway Corporation, is crucial for facilitating goods movement and addressing chronic congestion at Apapa ports, which have caused substantial financial losses. Calls during the 23rd Nigerian Economic Summit for intermodal transportation improvements emphasize enhancing railway and inland waterway connectivity to ports. Integrating rail and inland waterways would ease road network pressure, expedite goods movement, and foster national development. These initiatives promise substantial benefits for Nigeria's competitiveness globally and underline their positive impact on overall development prospects.

Theoretical Framework

The exploration of this topic is grounded in dependency theory, which examines foreign influence on the political economies of developing countries. Originating from Marxist-Leninist ideology, dependency theory, as outlined by Dos Santos (1971), describes a scenario where the economies of certain nations are shaped by the growth and expansion of other economies to which they are subjugated. This theory seeks to identify the factors contributing to the underdevelopment of certain countries, asserting that resources flow from impoverished "periphery" nations to affluent "core" nations, enriching the latter at the former's expense. Proponents of dependency theory argue that the integration of poor states into the global economy

perpetuates their poverty while enriching wealthier states. The theory's core premises include:

- a) Impoverished states supply natural resources, cheap labour, markets for obsolete technology, and markets to wealthy nations, enabling the latter to maintain their high standards of living.
- b) Wealthy nations actively sustain a state of dependence through various means, including economic, media control, politics, banking and finance, education, culture, sport, and all aspects of human resource development.
- c) Wealthy states thwart attempts by dependent nations to resist their influence through economic sanctions or military force (Todaro, 2003).

Dependency theory challenges the notion that peripheral countries' poverty is solely due to their lack of or incomplete integration into the global system, as posited by free-market economists. Instead, it emphasises how these countries are integrated into the system. Within this framework, there are two perspectives: bourgeois scholars and radical scholars of neo-Marxian political economy.

Bourgeois scholars attribute the underdevelopment and dependency of most Third World countries (TWCs) to internal factors such as lack of integration, capital diffusion, technological and institutional shortcomings, poor governance, corruption, and mismanagement. They view these issues as internally generated rather than externally imposed. According to this perspective, solutions involve seeking foreign assistance through aid, loans, investments, and allowing multinational corporations (MNCs) to operate freely. They argue that MNCs facilitate development by transferring technology, capital, and management skills. However, critics argue that while bourgeois scholars' analysis appears compelling due to the socio-political challenges faced by TWCs, their explanations are superficial and serve to uphold capitalist interests.

Discussion of Finding

This research reveals that the foreign aid model has been predominantly used for executing infrastructure projects in Nigeria. Its effectiveness has been most notable in Lagos State, where authorities have partnered with the private sector for the design, financing, and management of public utilities. However, these projects often lack the sustainable management characteristics ideal in a foreign aid framework. Beyond Lagos State, a brief examination of infrastructure procurement by state governments indicates a continued reliance on the traditional model of awarding contracts to private firms for project execution, designed and financed by the governments themselves. Consequently, Nigeria has generally underperformed in meeting its infrastructure needs, despite the country's developmental potential.

Foreign aid serves as a vital lifeline for developing nations, and in Nigeria, infrastructure development heavily relies on this assistance. Therefore, prioritising capacity development initiatives within Nigeria is imperative to enhance aid programming, coordination, and management processes. This must be done following the principles of harmonisation, alignment, and mutual accountability to ensure better outcomes in both foreign aid and infrastructural development management. Substantial reform of foreign aid is required to rejuvenate programmes and realign priorities, with a focus on areas in dire need of developed infrastructure. Establishing robust infrastructural facilities and institutional frameworks for monitoring and evaluating the inflow and utilisation of foreign aid is essential for ensuring transparency and effectiveness in aid management.

A reliable and efficient transportation system is crucial for economic growth in any region. Such a system facilitates regional access, essential for the smooth functioning of markets for manufacturing, retail, labour, and housing. Transportation plays a pivotal role in economic growth and development, constituting a wealth-generating industry. Inadequate transportation infrastructure hampers a nation's ability to utilise its natural resources, distribute goods, integrate manufacturing and agriculture sectors, and provide essential services such as education and healthcare.

Maintaining and enhancing existing transportation infrastructure while investing in new facilities is imperative for fostering national wealth. National wealth, measured by gross domestic product (GDP), is a crucial indicator of economic growth. Improved transportation systems contribute to economic prosperity by raising income levels and improving people's living standards. Additionally, transportation infrastructure development serves to maintain or enhance economic opportunities, quality of life, and income levels for residents of a particular region. This makes transportation planning, especially the development of railway transport, a priority for Nigeria, reducing production costs and enhancing competitiveness with industries abroad.

5.2 Conclusion

In conclusion, comprehensive reform across all sectors of Nigeria's economy is crucial. Donors should carefully assess recipients' commitment to reform initiatives, collaborating closely with experts and local communities. Targeting foreign aid to specific sectoral needs is essential for achieving meaningful development outcomes and avoiding resource wastage.

Donor governments and multilateral institutions must continue advocating for economic reforms within recipient governments to enhance aid effectiveness and reduce dependency over time. A significant challenge lies in the lack of political continuity, where successive administrations may neglect previous policies.

Concessionaires often expedite project completion to avoid cost increases with changing administrations. Without steadfast commitment to success, vested interests in Nigeria may undermine efforts to promote public-private partnerships (PPPs). Foreign aid and infrastructure projects in Nigeria encounter opposition from unions, civil servants, and socio-economic groups. Misunderstandings about the PPPs further complicate matters. Rail transport, vital for economic development, supports production, distribution, and connectivity across various sectors, acting as a cornerstone of the national transportation network.

5.4 Recommendations

Based on these findings, the study proposes several recommendations. :

- 1. Strengthen Legal Frameworks:** Ensuring robust provisions within the legal framework is critical to safeguarding the interests of investors and financiers, a persistent challenge for international aid in Nigeria and similar developing countries.
- 2. Establish an Infrastructural Bank:** Setting up an infrastructure bank to consolidate aid from donor nations within the recipient country is essential. Additionally, collaborating with commercial and industrial banks to provide financial expertise will enhance the effective management of foreign aid.
- 3. Capacity Development:** Conducting capacity development activities in Nigeria is imperative to improve aid programming, coordination, and management processes, aligning with principles of harmonisation, alignment, and mutual accountability. This approach promises more effective allocation of foreign aid for infrastructural development.
- 4. Reform Foreign Aid Programmes:** Undertaking significant reforms of foreign aid is critical to revitalise programmes and refocus priorities on areas with pressing infrastructural needs.
- 5. Establishing robust monitoring and evaluation frameworks:** Establishing robust infrastructural facilities and institutional frameworks to monitor and evaluate the inflow and utilisation of foreign aid is crucial. Effective government oversight, particularly through the supervising ministry, is essential to ensure transparent and accountable use of funds.

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